

UDC: 616.857-053.2(497.115)

PEDIATRIC AGE-HEADACHES IN OUR CLINICAL EXPERIENCE

Armend Vuçitërna¹, Ramush Bejiqi², Arlinda Maloku², Arbona Sadiki², Krenare Shehu²,
Nurse Blerta Vuçitërna², Drita Telaku², Abdurrahim Gerguri², Naim Zeka², Ragip Retkoceri²,
Dritero Dobra², Armend Kërveshi², Rinor Bejiqi², F Aliu²

Clinical centre University of Kosovo, College of Medical sciences "Rezonanca"

Received: 2017-03-10

Accepted: 2017-04-20

Published online: 2017-04-30

Introduction

Headaches are one of the most frequent causes of hospital admission in Pediatric Neurology, not only because of the frequency, but even for the state of causing suffering to children. The possibility of the existence of serious diseases that can be detected, alert both parents and neurologist.

Study methods: The study was performed in University Clinical Center of Kosovo, Pediatric Clinic, and Neurology unit. Aim of the study was to collect epidemiological clinical and diagnostic data in a group of patients admitted in our unit. The study was performed during the period 2014-2016. Study is retrospective; study included 58 children affected by headache. 31 cases or (53.4%) of patients were hospitalized with acute headache, the remaining 27 (46.5%) were hospitalized because of an intense episode of a recurrent headache for some time.

In diagnostic practice as the main objective was differentiation of headaches in Primary or essential.

Results

From our study came out that the largest number belonged to children from 7-14 years, while the average age of the most affected children is 12-13 years. Comparing to the gender females were more affected in this age when puberty starts.

Secondary or symptomatic diseases of intra or extra cranial, or systemic diseases.

In this case they were identified:

30(51, 7%) cases with secondary headaches
20 cases with febrile acute illness, 6 of them with frontal and maxillary sinusitis
7 cases with cranial trauma
1 case of meningitis
1 case of acute encephalopathy
1 case with arterial hypertension
28 cases with primary headaches (48, 3%)
15 cases usual hemicranias
4 cases of hemicranias with aura
1 cases of confusion hemicranias
8 cases of tense headaches

In the case of primary headaches we secure parents and patients for benign disease progression to avoid additional unnecessary hospitalizations and disappointing for both sides. Suggested elimination of the explosive factors: consulted infusing attack ordinary analgesics therapy as fast onset of the crisis, and regular visits.

During a period of four months: in 22/28 (78.5%) we achieved better control of headache symptomatology.

In 6/28 of cases (21, 5%) persistence and intensity of symptoms demanded prophylactic therapy.

CONCLUSION

In our research requirements for the treatment of primitive headaches were about 48.5%, while in our reality migraine and headaches of intensively type are pathologies that are often overlooked and misdiagnosed.

Despite the fact that about 80% of patients that we have been observed in the preceding months have had other episodes of headaches that were affecting their daily activities, only 20% of their diagnosis had been correct at the time were examined.

It is necessary, that parents and the treating physician have more sensibility for this problem. Teachers in particular can play an important role, when they notice changes in the behavior of children they should suggest a medical examination.

Based in our experience we noticed:

50 % of patients are cured

34 % of patient's headaches are improved after 3-4 years

24% of patients continue to have headaches in adult age

In treated cases has been noticed a great tendency of chronicity

Setting the headache diagnosis is not just too characterized symptoms, and described carefully what happens, but we also need to talk briefly about all aspects of the child's psychology, also the adolescent and family to achieve good results in benefit of the patient.

REFERENCES

1. Academy of Neurology and the Practice Committee of the Child Neurology Society. Neurology 2002; 59:490-498.
2. Barlow, CF. Headaches and migraine in childhood. Philadelphia and Oxford: Blackwell, 1984.
3. Bures, J., Buresova, O., Krivanek, J. The mechanism and applications of Leao's spreading depression of electroencephalographic activity. Neë York: Academic Press, 1974.

4. Chang, M., Rapoport, AM. Acute treatment of migraine headache. *Tech Reg Anesth Pain Manag.* 2009. 9-15.
5. Chu, ML., Shinnar, S. Headaches in children younger than 7 years of age. *Arch Neurol* 1992;49:79-82
6. DeRomanis, F., Buzzi, MG., Assensa, S., et al. Basilar migraine with electroencephalographic findings of occipital spike-wave complexes: a long-term study in seven children. *Cephalalgia* 1993; 13:192-196.
7. Egger, J., Carter, CM., Wilson, J., et al. Is migraine a food allergy? *Lancet* 1983; 2:865-869.
8. Finocchi, C., Sivori, G., Food as trigger and aggravating factor of migraine. *Neurological Sciences.* 2012; 33:77-80
9. Goadsby, PJ., Silberstein SD. Migraine triggers: Harnessing the messages of clinical practice. *Neurology.*2013; 80:424-425.
10. Graham, JR., Wolff HG. Mechanism of migraine headache and action of ergotamine tartrate. *Arch Neurol Psychiatry* 1938; 39:737-763.
11. Headache Classification Subcommittee of the International Headache Society The International classification of headache disorders, 3rd edition (beta version) *Cephalalgia.* 2013; 33: 629-808.
12. Kelman, L. The triggers or precipitants of the acute migraine attack. *Cephalalgia* 2007; 27:394-402.
13. Lewis, DW., Ashwal, S., Dahl G., et al. Practice parameter: evaluation of children and adolescents with recurrent headaches: report of the Quality Standards Subcommittee of the American
14. Lewis, DW., Qureshi FA. Acute headache in the pediatric emergency department. *Headache* 2000; 40: 200-203.
15. Lewis DE. Headaches in children and adolescents. *Curr Probl Pediatr Adolesc Health Care.* 2007 Jul. 37(6):207-46.
16. Lipton, RB., Stewart, WF., Diamond, S., et al. Prevalence and burden of migraine in the United States: data from the American Migraine Study II. *Headache* 2001; 41:646-657.
17. Lj, S., Hagen, K., Jensen, R., Katsarava, Z., Lipton, R., Scher, A., Steiner, T., Zwart, JA. The global burden of headache: a documentation of headache prevalence and disability worldwide. *Cephalalgia.* 2007; 27:193-210.
18. Winner, P., Rothner, AD., eds. *Headache in children and adolescents.* Hamilton and London: B.C. Decker, 2001.